

Some Results of Neutrosophic Relations for Neutrosophic Set Theory

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Abstract:

Nearly thirty years ago, the science of Neutrosophic appeared at the hands of the scientist Smarandache, who generalized the concept of the intuitionistic set to the neutrosophic set and the intuitionistic logic into the neutrosophic logic according to the degree of membership functions truth, indeterminacy, and falsehood respectively. Moreover, he presented the neutrosophic structure of a set when he studied the structure of neutrosophic algebra with other scholars in their works neutrosophic groups, and neutrosophic rings. Later, a few scholars who take the concept of neutrosophic structure of set to construct neutrosophic Number theory and Neutrosophic linear algebra. In our previous work, we introduced some classification of a neutrosophic set to three types related to classical sets and built a new structure of neutrosophic set theory. This article addressed new facts of neutrosophic relations on neutrosophic sets of three types. This article includes a neutrosophic partial order relation on $H_i^t[I]$, where $i = 1,2,3$ with a few theorems and examples.

Keywords: Neutrosophic sets $H_i^t[I]$, $i = 1,2,3$; Neutrosophic partial order relation on $H_i^t[I]$; Properties Neutrosophic partial order relation on $H_i^t[I]$;

1. Introduction

In [1], [2], and [3] we presented neutrosophic set theory related to the neutrosophic sets of three types as construction from classical sets and investigated many theorems and examples with the neutrosophic binary operations such as neutrosophic; union, intersection, complement, differences, symmetric differences, cartesian products with their properties. In addition, the generalization of neutrosophic operations are studied. The present article extended the previous work and addressed to some results about neutrosophic relation on neutrosophic sets of three types. This paper focuses

on partial order relation on neutrosophic sets of three types with some theorems and examples. The neutrosophic number of the form $N_1 = a + bI$, where I is literal in indeterminacy, $I^2 = I$, and $0I = 0$ proposed by Smarandache when presented structure of neutrosophic algebra such as neutrosophic groups, neutrosophic rings and so on, see for example [4], [5]. Moreover, we use the neutrosophic number of the form $N_1 = a + bI$ in some neutrosophic algebra structure such as neutrosophic linear algebra in [6] and [7], neutrosophic rings in [8], and neutrosophic groups in [9] and [10].

2. Some Neutrosophic Relations on Neutrosophic sets of three types

In this section, we shall present new information about neutrosophic relations on neutrosophic sets of three types. In mathematical thinking, describing the sets and classifying them is very important to treat with them, and after that, how to define the operations, relations, and functions on them. In many different neutrosophic sets there are neutrosophic relations which hold between certain neutrosophic pairs of neutrosophic elements.

Definition 2.1 [1] Let $H \neq \emptyset \subset U$ be a non-empty-set, then;

1. $H_1^t[I] = \{h_1 + h_2I : h_1, h_2 \in H\}$ is a neutrosophic-set of type-1,
2. $H_2^t[I] = \{aI \cup \{a\} : a \in H\}$ is a neutrosophic-set of type-2, and
3. $H_3^t[I] = \{(h_1 + h_2I) \cup \{h_1\} : h_1, h_2 \in H\}$ is a neutrosophic-sets of type-3, where I is an indeterminacy

Definition 2.2 [3] Let $H_i^t[I]$ and $N_i^t[I]$ be two neutrosophic sets of three types, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$.

The neutrosophic cartesian product denoted by $H_i^t[I] \times N_i^t[I]$, and defined by:

$$H_i^t[I] \times N_i^t[I] = \{(h, n) : h \in H_i^t[I] \wedge n \in N_i^t[I]\} \\ = \{(h, n) : \exists h_1, h_2 \in H \wedge \exists n_1, n_2 \in N, h = h_1 + h_2I, n = n_1 + n_2I\}, \text{ where } I \text{ is an indeterminacy.}$$

Theorem 2.1 [3] Let $H_i^t[I]$ and $N_i^t[I]$ be two neutrosophic sets of three types, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$, and let $\langle h, n \rangle$ and $\langle h', n' \rangle$ be two neutrosophic order pairs belongs to $H_i^t[I] \times N_i^t[I]$. Then $\langle h, n \rangle = \langle h', n' \rangle \Leftrightarrow h = h' \wedge n = n' \Leftrightarrow (h_1 = h'_1 \wedge h_2 = h'_2) \wedge (n_1 = n'_1 \wedge n_2 = n'_2)$.

Definition 2.3 A neutrosophic binary relation $\mathfrak{R}$ from a neutrosophic sets of three types $H_i^t[I]$ into a neutrosophic sets of three types $N_i^t[I]$ is a neutrosophic subset of neutrosophic cartesian product of $H_i^t[I] \times N_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$.

Observation.

- If $\langle h, n \rangle \in \mathfrak{R} \Leftrightarrow h\mathfrak{R}n$ or $\mathfrak{R}(h) = n$, and we say that h is neutrosophic related to n or n is in neutrosophic relation with h .
- If $H_i^t[I] = N_i^t[I]$, then we say that $\mathfrak{R}$ is a neutrosophic binary relations on $H_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$.
- All neutrosophic operations defined in [1], [3], and [2] can be defined on neutrosophic relation $\mathfrak{R}$.
- If $\mathfrak{R}$ is a binary neutrosophic relation on $H_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$, then $\mathfrak{R} \subset H_i^t[I] \times H_i^t[I]$.

Definition 2.4 Let $\mathfrak{R}$ be a neutrosophic relation from neutrosophic set $H_i^t[I]$ into a neutrosophic set $N_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1,2,3$. Define a neutrosophic domain of $\mathfrak{R}$, written $NeuDom(\mathfrak{R})$ as the following:

$$NeuDom(\mathfrak{R}) = \{x \in H_i^t[I] : \exists y \in N_i^t[I] \text{ such that } \mathfrak{R}(x) = y\}, \text{ for any } i = 1,2,3$$

$$= \{\exists x_1, x_2 \in H : \exists y_1, y_2 \in N \text{ such that } \mathfrak{R}(x_1 + x_2I) = \mathfrak{R}(x_1) + \mathfrak{R}(x_2I) = y_1 + y_2I\}, \text{ for any } i = 1,2,3 \text{ and indeterminacy } I.$$

Definition 2.5 Let $\mathfrak{R}$ be a neutrosophic relation from neutrosophic set $H_i^t[I]$ into a neutrosophic set $N_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1,2,3$. Define a neutrosophic co-domain of $\mathfrak{R}$, written $NeuCdom(\mathfrak{R})$ as the following:

$$NeuCdom(\mathfrak{R}) = \{\forall y \in N_i^t[I] : \exists x \in H_i^t[I] \text{ such that } \langle x, y \rangle \in \mathfrak{R} \subseteq N_i^t[I]\}, \text{ for any } i = 1,2,3$$

$$= \{\forall y_1, y_2 \in N : \exists x_1, x_2 \in H \text{ such that } \langle (x_1 + x_2I), (y_1 + y_2I) \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}\}, \text{ for any } i = 1,2,3 \text{ and indeterminacy } I.$$

Definition 2.6 Let $H_i^t[I]$ and $N_i^t[I]$ be two neutrosophic sets of three types, for any $i = 1,2,3$, and let $\langle h, n \rangle$ and $\langle h', n' \rangle$ be two neutrosophic order pairs belongs to $\mathfrak{R} \subseteq H_i^t[I] \times N_i^t[I]$. Then

1. $\langle h, n \rangle < \langle h', n' \rangle \Leftrightarrow h < h' \wedge n < n'$
 $\Leftrightarrow (h_1 < h'_1 \wedge h_2 < h'_2) \wedge (n_1 < n'_1 \wedge n_2 < n'_2), \forall \langle h, n \rangle, \langle h', n' \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}.$

We say that the neutrosophic order pair $\langle h, n \rangle$ less than the neutrosophic order pair $\langle h', n' \rangle$. The dualism of $<$ is given by $>$.

2. $\langle h, n \rangle \leq \langle h', n' \rangle \Leftrightarrow h \leq h' \wedge n \leq n'$

$$\Leftrightarrow (((h_1 < h'_1) \vee h_1 = h'_1) \wedge ((h_2 < h'_2) \vee h_2 = h'_2)) \wedge$$

$$(((n_1 < n'_1) \vee n_1 = n'_1) \wedge ((n_2 < n'_2) \vee n_2 = n'_2)), \forall \langle h, n \rangle, \langle h', n' \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}.$$

The dualism of $\leq$ is given by $\geq$.

Example 2.1 Let $H = \{1,5\}$ and $N = \{2,4,6\}$ be two classical sets. Then the classical set of relation R from H into N such that $R = \{(x, y) \in H \times N : x < y\}$,

$$R = \{(1,2), (1,4), (1,6), (5,6)\}.$$

Now, consider the neutrosophic set $H_i^t[I]$ of types 1, and $N_i^t[I]$ of types 1 are given by:

$$H_1^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{matrix} 1 + 1I, & 1 + 5I, \\ 5 + 1I, & 5 + 5I \end{matrix} \right\}, \text{ and } N_1^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{matrix} 2 + 2I, & 2 + 4I, & 2 + 6I, \\ 4 + 2I, & 4 + 4I, & 4 + 6I, \\ 6 + 2I, & 6 + 4I, & 6 + 6I, \end{matrix} \right\}. \text{ The neutrosophic cartesian}$$

product of $H_1^t[I] \times N_1^t[I]$ is given by:

$$H_1^t[I] \times N_1^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{matrix} \langle 1 + 1I, 2 + 2I \rangle, \dots \langle 1 + 1I, 4 + 2I \rangle, \dots \langle 1 + 1I, 6 + 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 1 + 5I, 2 + 2I \rangle, \dots \langle 1 + 5I, 4 + 2I \rangle, \dots \langle 1 + 5I, 6 + 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 5 + 1I, 2 + 2I \rangle, \dots \langle 5 + 1I, 4 + 2I \rangle, \dots \langle 5 + 1I, 6 + 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 5 + 5I, 2 + 2I \rangle, \dots \langle 5 + 5I, 4 + 2I \rangle, \dots \langle 5 + 5I, 6 + 6I \rangle, \end{matrix} \right\}. \text{ Define a neutrosophic}$$

relation $\mathfrak{R}_1$ as $\mathfrak{R}_1 = \{\langle h, n \rangle \in H_1^t[I] \times N_1^t[I] : h < n\}$,

$\mathfrak{R}_1 = \{\langle h, n \rangle \in H_1^t[I] \times N_1^t[I] : (h_1 + h_2I) < (n_1 + n_2I)\}$, for some $h_1, h_2 \in H$ and $n_1, n_2 \in N$,

$\mathfrak{R}_1 = \{\langle h, n \rangle \in H_1^t[I] \times N_1^t[I] : ((h_1 < n_1) \wedge (h_2 < n_2))\}$, for some $h_1, h_2 \in H$ and $n_1, n_2 \in N$,

$$\mathfrak{R}_1 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle 1 + 1I, 2 + 2I \rangle, \langle 1 + 1I, 2 + 4I \rangle, \langle 1 + 1I, 2 + 6I \rangle, \dots, \langle 1 + 1I, 6 + 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 1 + 5I, 2 + 6I \rangle, \langle 1 + 5I, 2 + 6I \rangle, \langle 1 + 5I, 6 + 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 5 + 1I, 6 + 2I \rangle, \langle 5 + 1I, 6 + 4I \rangle, \langle 5 + 1I, 6 + 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 5 + 5I, 6 + 6I \rangle, \end{array} \right\}. \text{ Then the}$$

neutrosophic domain and co-domain are represented by:

$$NeuDom(\mathfrak{R}_1) = \{1 + 1I, 1 + 5I, 5 + 1I, 5 + 5I\}, \text{ and}$$

$$NeuCdom(\mathfrak{R}_1) = \{2 + 2I, 2 + 4I, 2 + 6I, \dots, 6 + 6I, 2 + 6I, 6 + 2I, 6 + 4I, 6 + 6I\}$$

If we consider the neutrosophic sets $H_2^t[I]$, and $N_2^t[I]$ of types 2, we have

$$H_2^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1, \\ 5, \end{array} \begin{array}{l} 1I \\ 5I \end{array} \right\}, \text{ and } N_2^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2, \\ 4, \\ 6, \end{array} \begin{array}{l} 2I \\ 4I \\ 6I \end{array} \right\}. \text{ The neutrosophic cartesian product of } H_2^t[I] \times N_2^t[I] \text{ is}$$

$$\text{given by: } H_2^t[I] \times N_2^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle 1, 2 \rangle, \langle 1, 4 \rangle, \langle 1, 6 \rangle, \langle 1, 2I \rangle, \langle 1, 4I \rangle, \langle 1, 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 1I, 2 \rangle, \langle 1I, 4 \rangle, \langle 1I, 6 \rangle, \langle 1I, 2I \rangle, \langle 1I, 4I \rangle, \langle 1I, 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 5, 2 \rangle, \langle 5, 4 \rangle, \langle 5, 6 \rangle, \langle 5, 2I \rangle, \langle 5, 4I \rangle, \langle 5, 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 5I, 2 \rangle, \langle 5I, 4 \rangle, \langle 5I, 6 \rangle, \langle 5I, 2I \rangle, \langle 5I, 4I \rangle, \langle 5I, 6I \rangle \end{array} \right\}. \text{ Define a neutrosophic}$$

relation $\mathfrak{R}_2$ as $\mathfrak{R}_2 = \{ \langle h, n \rangle \in H_2^t[I] \times N_2^t[I] : h < n \}$,

$\mathfrak{R}_2 = \{ \langle h, n \rangle \in H_2^t[I] \times N_2^t[I] : h < n \}$, for some $h \in H$ and $n \in N$, then the neutrosophic set relation $\mathfrak{R}_2$ becomes like:

$$\mathfrak{R}_2 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle 1, 2 \rangle, \langle 1, 4 \rangle, \langle 1, 6 \rangle, \langle 1, 2I \rangle, \langle 1, 4I \rangle, \langle 1, 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 1I, 2 \rangle, \langle 1I, 4 \rangle, \langle 1I, 6 \rangle, \langle 1I, 2I \rangle, \langle 1I, 4I \rangle, \langle 1I, 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 5, 6 \rangle, \langle 5, 6I \rangle, \\ \langle 5I, 6I \rangle \end{array} \right\}, \text{ and the neutrosophic domain and co-domain}$$

are given by: $NeuDom(\mathfrak{R}_2) = \{1, 1I, 5, 5I\}$, and $NeuCdom(\mathfrak{R}_2) = \{2, 4, 6, 2I, 4I, 6I\}$.

Definition 2.7 Let $H_1^t[I]$, and $H_3^t[I]$, be a neutrosophic-set of type-1, and type 3 respectively. Let be $x, y, z \in H_1^t[I]$. Define $\preceq$ is a partially ordered neutrosophic-set of type-1 as following:

- i. PN_1 : (Neutrosophic Reflexive Axiom): $x \preceq x \Leftrightarrow (x_1 \preceq x_1) \wedge (x_2 \preceq x_2), \forall x \in H_1^t[I]$,
- ii. PN_2 : (Neutrosophic Antisymmetric Axiom):
 $((x \preceq y) \wedge (y \preceq x) \Rightarrow x = y) \Leftrightarrow ((x_1 \preceq y_1) \wedge (x_2 \preceq y_2)) \wedge ((y_1 \preceq x_1) \wedge (y_2 \preceq x_2))$
 $\Rightarrow ((x_1 = y_1) \wedge (x_2 = y_2)), \forall x, y \in H_1^t[I]$, and
- iii. PN_3 : (Neutrosophic Transitive Axiom):
 $((x \preceq y) \wedge (y \preceq z) \Rightarrow x \preceq z) \Leftrightarrow ((x_1 \preceq y_1) \wedge (x_2 \preceq y_2)) \wedge ((y_1 \preceq z_1) \wedge (y_2 \preceq z_2))$
 $\Rightarrow ((x_1 \preceq z_1) \wedge (x_2 \preceq z_2)), \forall x, y, z \in H_1^t[I]$.

If the neutrosophic relation $\preceq$ is a partially neutrosophic orders on $H_1^t[I]$, then we said that $H_1^t[I]$ is a partially order set under $\preceq$. If the neutrosophic relation is given by $<$, then we said that $<$ is strictly neutrosophic orders of $H_1^t[I]$.

Observation. $x \preceq y$ is reading x precedes y or y dominates x . The definition 2.7 is working with the neutrosophic set $H_3^t[I]$ of type-3. We need to define partially ordered neutrosophic set of type-2.

Definition 2.8 Let $H_2^t[I]$ be a neutrosophic-set of type-2 and let be $x, y, z \in H_2^t[I]$. Define $\preceq$ is a partially ordered neutrosophic set of type-2 as the following:

- PN_1 . (Neutrosophic Reflexive Axiom): $x \preceq x, \forall x \in H_2^t[I]$, and indeterminacy I .
- PN_2 . (Neutrosophic Antisymmetric Axiom): $((x \preceq y) \wedge (y \preceq x) \Rightarrow x = y), \forall x, y \in H_2^t[I]$, and
- PN_3 . (Neutrosophic Transitive Axiom): $((x \preceq y) \wedge (y \preceq z) \Rightarrow x \preceq z), \forall x, y, z \in H_2^t[I]$.

If the neutrosophic relation $\preceq$ is a partially neutrosophic orders on $H_2^t[I]$, then we said that $H_2^t[I]$ is a partially order set under $\preceq$. If the neutrosophic relation is given by $<$, then we said that $<$ is strictly neutrosophic orders of $H_2^t[I]$.

Theorem 2.2 Let $\mathbb{N} = \{0,1,2, \dots\}$ be the set of natural numbers. Then the neutrosophic-natural numbers of type-1 is given by:

$$\mathbb{N}_1^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{matrix} 0, & 0 + I, & 0 + 2I, & 0 + 3I, & \dots \\ 1, & 1 + I, & 1 + 2I, & 1 + 3I, & \dots \\ 2, & 2 + I, & 2 + 2I, & 2 + 3I, & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots \end{matrix} \right\}. \text{ For any } x, y \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I], \text{ we define the neutrosophic}$$

orders relation $x \preceq y \Leftrightarrow x \leq y$ " x less than or equal to y ".

$$\Leftrightarrow \exists x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } (x_1 \leq y_1) \wedge (x_2 \leq y_2), \forall x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{N}. \text{ Then}$$

The neutrosophic relation less than or equal $\leq$ is a neutrosophic partial order relation on $\mathbb{N}_1^t[I]$.

Proof.

PN_1 . Since, $(x_1 \leq x_1) \wedge (x_2 \leq x_2), \forall x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{N} \Rightarrow (x_1 \leq x_1) \wedge (x_2 I \leq x_2 I)$

$\Rightarrow (x_1 + x_2 I \leq x_1 + x_2 I) \Rightarrow x \leq x, \forall x \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I]$, thus $\leq$ is a neutrosophic reflexive relation.

PN_2 . Suppose that $\forall x, y \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I], ((x \leq y) \wedge (y \leq x)) \Rightarrow \exists x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{N}$, and I is an indeterminacy with $x = x_1 + x_2 I, y = y_1 + y_2 I$ such that

$$((x_1 \leq y_1) \wedge (x_2 \leq y_2)) \wedge ((y_1 \leq x_1) \wedge (y_2 \leq x_2)), \text{ since } ((x_1 \leq y_1) \wedge (y_1 \leq x_1)) \Rightarrow (x_1 = y_1) \quad (1).$$

$$\text{Also, since } ((x_2 \leq y_2) \wedge (y_2 \leq x_2)) \Rightarrow (x_2 = y_2) \quad (2).$$

From (1) and (2) we have $(x_1 = y_1) \wedge (x_2 = y_2) \Rightarrow (x_1 = y_1) \wedge (x_2 I = y_2 I)$

$\Rightarrow x_1 + x_2 I = y_1 + y_2 I \Rightarrow x = y$. Hence $\leq$ is a neutrosophic antisymmetric relation.

PN_3 . Suppose that $\forall x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I], ((x \leq y) \wedge (y \leq z)) \Rightarrow \exists x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2, z_1, z_2 \in \mathbb{N}$, and I is an indeterminacy with $x = x_1 + x_2 I, y = y_1 + y_2 I$, and $z = z_1 + z_2 I$, such that

$$((x_1 \leq y_1) \wedge (x_2 \leq y_2)) \wedge ((y_1 \leq z_1) \wedge (y_2 \leq z_2)).$$

$$\text{Since, } ((x_1 \leq y_1) \wedge (y_1 \leq z_1)), \text{ we deduce that } (x_1 \leq z_1) \quad (1).$$

$$\text{Since, } ((x_2 \leq y_2) \wedge (y_2 \leq z_2)), \text{ we get } (x_2 \leq z_2) \quad (2).$$

From (1) and (2) we have $(x_1 \leq z_1) \wedge (x_2 \leq z_2) \Rightarrow (x_1 \leq z_1) \wedge (x_2 I \leq z_2 I)$, for any indeterminacy I

$\Rightarrow x_1 + x_2 I \leq z_1 + z_2 I \Rightarrow x \leq z$. Hence $\leq$ is a neutrosophic transitive relation. Thus $\mathbb{N}_1^t[I]$ is a partially order set under neutrosophic relation less than or equal $\leq$. Recall that $\mathbb{N}_1^t[I] = \mathbb{N}_3^t[I]$. ■

Theorem 2.3 Let $\mathbb{N} = \{0,1,2, \dots\}$ be the set of natural numbers. Then the neutrosophic-natural

numbers of type-2 is given by: $\mathbb{N}_2^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{matrix} 0, & 0I, \\ 1, & 1I, \\ 2, & 2I \\ \vdots & \vdots \end{matrix} \right\}$. For any $x, y \in \mathbb{N}_2^t[I]$, we define the neutrosophic

orders relation $(\forall x, y \in \mathbb{N}_2^t[I]), (x \preceq y \Leftrightarrow x \leq y \Rightarrow xI \leq yI)$ " x less than or equal to y ". Then The neutrosophic relation less than or equal $\leq$ is a neutrosophic partial order relation on $\mathbb{N}_2^t[I]$.

Proof.

PN_1 . since $(x \leq x), \forall x \in \mathbb{N} \Rightarrow (xI \leq xI), \forall x \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I]$. Hence $\leq$ is a neutrosophic reflexive relation.

PN_2 . Suppose that $\forall x, y \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I], ((x \leq y) \wedge (y \leq x)) \Rightarrow ((xI \leq yI) \wedge (yI \leq xI))$

$\Rightarrow (x = y) \wedge (xI = yI)$, where I is an indeterminacy. Therefore $\leq$ is a neutrosophic antisymmetric relation.

PN_3 . Suppose that $\forall x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I], ((x \leq y) \wedge (y \leq z)) \Rightarrow ((xI \leq yI) \wedge (yI \leq zI))$

$\Rightarrow (x \leq z) \wedge (xI \leq zI)$. Therefore $\leq$ is a neutrosophic transitive relation. Thus $\mathbb{N}_2^t[I]$ is a partially order set under neutrosophic relation less than or equal $\leq$. ■

Theorem 2.4 Let $\mathbb{N} = \{0,1,2, \dots\}$ be the set of natural numbers. Then the neutrosophic natural numbers of type-1 is given by:

$$\mathbb{N}_1^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{matrix} 0, & 0 + I, & 0 + 2I, & 0 + 3I, & \dots \\ 1, & 1 + I, & 1 + 2I, & 1 + 3I, & \dots \\ 2, & 2 + I, & 2 + 2I, & 2 + 3I, & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots \end{matrix} \right\}. \text{ For any } x, y \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I], \text{ we define the neutrosophic}$$

orders relation $\preceq$ as following:

$$\begin{aligned} \preceq &= \{ \langle x, y \rangle \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I] \times \mathbb{N}_1^t[I] : x|y, x \text{ divides } y \text{ in } \mathbb{N}_1^t[I] \} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \{ \langle x, y \rangle \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I] \times \mathbb{N}_1^t[I] : x_1 + x_2I | y_1 + y_2I, \text{ form some } x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{N} \}, \text{ and indeterminacy } I. \\ &\Leftrightarrow \{ \langle x, y \rangle \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I] \times \mathbb{N}_1^t[I] : x_1|y_1 \wedge x_2|y_2, \text{ form some } x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{N} \}, \text{ and indeterminacy } I. \end{aligned}$$

Then the neutrosophic relation $\preceq$ is a neutrosophic partial order relation on $\mathbb{N}_1^t[I]$.

Proof.

PN₁. Since $x_1 = 1.x_1$ and $x_2 = 1.x_2$, therefore $x_1 = 1.x_1$ and $x_2I = 1.x_2I$, for any indeterminacy I , implies that $(x_1|x_1 \wedge x_2|x_2), \forall x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{N}$, hence $(x_1|x_1 \wedge x_2I|x_2I), \forall x_1, x_2 \in \mathbb{N}$, for any indeterminacy I , we have $x_1+x_2I | x_1+x_2I \Rightarrow x|x, \forall x \in \mathbb{N}_1^t[I]$. Thus $|$ is a neutrosophic reflexive relation.

PN₂. Suppose that $\langle x, y \rangle \wedge \langle y, x \rangle \in \preceq$, from "neu-hypo", we have

$\langle x, y \rangle \in \preceq \Rightarrow x|y \Rightarrow \exists x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{N}$, and I is an indeterminacy with $x = x_1 + x_2I$, $y = y_1 + y_2I$ such that $x_1|y_1 \wedge x_2|y_2$. If $x_1|y_1 \Rightarrow \exists k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $y_1 = kx_1$, while if $x_2|y_2 \Rightarrow \exists k_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $y_2 = k_1x_2$. Furthermore, from "neu-hypo", we have

$\langle y, x \rangle \in \preceq \Rightarrow y|x \Rightarrow \exists x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{N}$, and I is an indeterminacy with $x = x_1 + x_2I$, $y = y_1 + y_2I$ such that $y_1|x_1 \wedge y_2|x_2$. If $y_1|x_1 \Rightarrow \exists k' \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $x_1 = k'y_1$, while if $y_2|x_2 \Rightarrow \exists k'_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $x_2 = k'_1y_2$. From pervious premises we have, $x_1 = k'y_1 = k'kx_1$, we deduce that $k'k = 1$, that is $k' = k = 1$, hence $x_1 = y_1$. By the same argue, we have $x_2 = k'_1y_2 = k'_1k_1x_2$, we deduce that $k'_1k_1 = 1$, that is $k'_1 = k_1 = 1$, hence $x_2 = y_2$, therefore $x_1+x_2I = y_1 + y_2I$, and consequently, $x = y$. Thus $|$ is a neutrosophic antisymmetric relation.

PN₂. Suppose that $\langle x, y \rangle \wedge \langle y, z \rangle \in \preceq$, from "neu-hypo", we have

$\langle x, y \rangle \in \preceq \Rightarrow x|y \Rightarrow \exists x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{N}$, and I is an indeterminacy with $x = x_1 + x_2I$, $y = y_1 + y_2I$ such that $x_1|y_1 \wedge x_2|y_2$. If $x_1|y_1 \Rightarrow \exists k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $y_1 = kx_1$, while if $x_2|y_2 \Rightarrow \exists k_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $y_2 = k_1x_2$. As $\langle y, z \rangle \in \preceq \Rightarrow y|z \Rightarrow \exists y_1, y_2, z_1, z_2 \in \mathbb{N}$, and I is an indeterminacy with $y = y_1 + y_2I$, $z = z_1 + z_2I$ such that $y_1|z_1 \wedge y_2|z_2$. If $y_1|z_1 \Rightarrow \exists k' \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $z_1 = k'y_1$, while if $y_2|z_2 \Rightarrow \exists k'_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $z_2 = k'_1y_2$. From pervious premises, we have $z_1 = k'y_1 = k'kx_1 = k''x$, where $k'' = k'k \in \mathbb{N}$. And $z_2 = k'_1y_2 = k'_1k_1x_2 = k''_1x_2$, where $k''_1 = k'_1k_1 \in \mathbb{N}$, therefore $x_1|z_1$ and $x_2|z_2$, hence $x_1|z_1$ and $x_2I|z_2I$, for any I , thus $x_1 + x_2I|z_1 + z_2I$, that is $x|z$, therefore $|$ is a neutrosophic transitive relation, and consequently, it is neutrosophic partial order relation. ■

Definition 2.9 [4] Let $\mathbb{Z}$ be a set of integer numbers and $\mathbb{Z}[I] = \{a + bI : a, b \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ be a neutrosophic-integer set, where $a + bI$ is a neutrosophic integer number.

Theorem 2.5 [8] Let $(\mathbb{Z}, +, \cdot)$ be a ring of integers under usual addition and multiplication, then the neutrosophic algebra structure (NAS): $N(\mathbb{Z}) = \langle \mathbb{Z}[I], +, \cdot \rangle$ is called the neutrosophic integer ring which is generated by I and $\mathbb{Z}$.

Definition 2.10 [1] Let $\mathbb{Z} = \{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots\}$ be the set of integers numbers. Then the neutrosophic-integer numbers of type-1 is given by:

$$\mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{matrix} 0, & 0 \pm I, & 0 \pm 2I, & 0 \pm 3I, & \dots \\ \pm 1, & \pm 1 \pm I, & \pm 1 \pm 2I, & \pm 1 \pm 3I, & \dots \\ \pm 2, & \pm 2 \pm I, & \pm 2 \pm 2I, & \pm 2 \pm 3I, & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Theorem 2.6 Let $\mathfrak{R}_3$ be a neutrosophic relation defined on $\mathbb{Z}_1^t[I]$ as the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{R}_3 &= \{ \langle h, n \rangle \in \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] \times \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] : h - n \leq 0 \} \\ &= \{ \langle h, n \rangle \in \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] \times \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] : (h_1 + h_2I) - (n_1 + n_2I) \leq 0, h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \} \\ &= \{ \langle h, n \rangle \in \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] \times \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] : (h_1 - n_1) + (h_2 - n_2)I \leq 0, h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \}. \end{aligned}$$

Then $\mathfrak{R}_3$ is a neutrosophic partial order relation on $\mathbb{Z}_1^t[I]$.

Proof.

PN_1 . Since $(h_1 - h_1) + (h_2 - h_2)I = 0 + 0I \leq 0 = 0 + 0I$, we have $\langle h, h \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_3, \forall h \in \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I]$, hence $\mathfrak{R}_3$ is a neutrosophic reflexive relation.

PN_2 . Suppose that $\langle h, n \rangle \wedge \langle n, h \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_3$. Since $\langle h, n \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_3 \Rightarrow h - n \leq 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow (h_1 + h_2I) - (n_1 + n_2I) &\leq 0, h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \\ \Rightarrow (h_1 + h_2I) &\leq (n_1 + n_2I), h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \\ \Rightarrow (h_1 \leq n_1) \wedge (h_2 &\leq n_2), h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Since $\langle n, h \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_3 \Rightarrow n - h \leq 0 \Rightarrow (n_1 + n_2I) - (h_1 + h_2I) \leq 0, h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow (n_1 + n_2I) &\leq (h_1 + h_2I), h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \\ \Rightarrow (n_1 \leq h_1) \wedge (n_2 &\leq h_2), h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

From (1) and (2) we have $(h_1 \leq n_1) \wedge (n_1 \leq h_1) \Rightarrow h_1 = n_1$ (3).

And $(h_2 \leq n_2) \wedge (n_2 \leq h_2) \Rightarrow h_2 = n_2$ (4).

By using (3) and (4) we have the premise $(h_1 = n_1) \wedge (h_2 = n_2)$, we deduced that $h = n$. Thus $\mathfrak{R}_3$ is a neutrosophic antisymmetric relation on $\mathbb{Z}_1^t[I]$.

PN_3 . Assume that $\langle h, n \rangle \wedge \langle n, m \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_3$. Since $\langle h, n \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_3 \Rightarrow h - n \leq 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow (h_1 + h_2I) - (n_1 + n_2I) &\leq 0, h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \\ \Rightarrow (h_1 + h_2I) &\leq (n_1 + n_2I), h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \\ \Rightarrow (h_1 \leq n_1) \wedge (h_2 &\leq n_2), h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Since $\langle n, m \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_3 \Rightarrow n - m \leq 0 \Rightarrow (n_1 + n_2I) - (m_1 + m_2I) \leq 0, m_1, m_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow (n_1 + n_2I) &\leq (m_1 + m_2I), m_1, m_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \\ \Rightarrow (n_1 \leq m_1) \wedge (n_2 &\leq m_2), m_1, m_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

From (1) and (2) we have $(h_1 \leq n_1) \wedge (n_1 \leq m_1) \Rightarrow (h_1 \leq m_1)$ (3).

And $(h_2 \leq n_2) \wedge (n_2 \leq m_2) \Rightarrow (h_2 \leq m_2)$ (4).

By using (3) and (4) we get $(h_1 \leq m_1) \wedge (h_2 \leq m_2) \Rightarrow (h_1 \leq m_1) \wedge (h_2I \leq m_2I)$

$$\Rightarrow h_1 + h_2I \leq m_1 + m_2I \Rightarrow h \leq m.$$

Therefore, $\mathfrak{R}_3$ is a neutrosophic transitive relation on $\mathbb{Z}_1^t[I]$. Hence $\mathfrak{R}_3$ is a neutrosophic partial order relation on $\mathbb{Z}_1^t[I]$. ■

Example 2.2 [1] Let $\mathbb{Z} = \{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots\}$ be the set of integers numbers. Then the neutrosophic-integer numbers of type-1 is given by:

$$\mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] = \left\{ \begin{array}{cccccc} 0, & 0 \pm I, & 0 \pm 2I, & 0 \pm 3I, & \dots & \\ \pm 1, & \pm 1 \pm I, & \pm 1 \pm 2I, & \pm 1 \pm 3I, & \dots & \\ \pm 2, & \pm 2 \pm I, & \pm 2 \pm 2I, & \pm 2 \pm 3I, & \dots & \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots \end{array} \right\}.$$

Let $\mathfrak{R}_4$ be a neutrosophic relation defined on $\mathbb{Z}_1^t[I]$ as the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{R}_4 &= \{ \langle h, n \rangle \in \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] \times \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] : x|y, x \text{ divides } y \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] \} \\ &= \{ \langle h, n \rangle \in \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] \times \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] : h_1 + h_2I | n_1 + n_2I, \text{ for some } h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z}, \text{ and indeterminacy } I. \\ &= \{ \langle h, n \rangle \in \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] \times \mathbb{Z}_1^t[I] : h_1 | n_1 \wedge h_2 | n_2, \text{ for some } h_1, h_2, n_1, n_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \}. \end{aligned}$$

Then $\mathfrak{R}_4$ is a non neutrosophic partial order relation on $\mathbb{Z}_1^t[I]$. By using the counter example,

$$\because -5 = (-1)5 \Rightarrow (5|-5) \wedge (5|-5) \Rightarrow (5|-5) \wedge (5I|-5I) \Rightarrow (5 + 5I|-5 + (-5)I) = -5 - 5I$$

$\therefore \langle 5 + 5I, -5 - 5I \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_4$. Also,
 $\because 5 = (-1)(-5) \Rightarrow (-5|5) \wedge (-5|5) \Rightarrow (-5|5) \wedge (-5I|5I) \Rightarrow (-5 - 5I|5 + 5I)$.
 $\therefore \langle -5 - 5I, 5 + 5I \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_4$. But $\langle 5 + 5I, -5 - 5I \rangle \neq \langle -5 - 5I, 5 + 5I \rangle$ by theorem 4.1 in [3].

Example 2.3 [1] Let $\mathbb{Z} = \{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots\}$ be the set of integers numbers. Then the neutrosophic-integer numbers of type-2 is given by:

$$\mathbb{Z}_2^t[I] = \begin{pmatrix} 0, & 0I, \\ \pm 1, & \pm 1I, \\ \pm 2, & \pm 2I \\ \vdots & \vdots \end{pmatrix}$$

Let $\mathfrak{R}_5$ be a neutrosophic relation defined on $\mathbb{Z}_2^t[I]$ as the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{R}_5 &= \{ \langle x, y \rangle \in \mathbb{Z}_2^t[I] \times \mathbb{Z}_2^t[I] : x|y, x \text{ divides } y \text{ in } \mathbb{Z}_2^t[I] \} \\ &= \{ \langle x, y \rangle \in \mathbb{Z}_2^t[I] \times \mathbb{Z}_2^t[I] : x|y \Leftrightarrow xI|yI \}, \text{ for any indeterminacy } I. \end{aligned}$$

Then $\mathfrak{R}_5$ is a non neutrosophic partial order relation on $\mathbb{Z}_2^t[I]$. By using the following counter example.

$\because -5 = (-1)5 \Rightarrow (5|-5) \wedge (5|-5) \Rightarrow (5|-5) \wedge (5I|-5I) \Rightarrow \langle 5, -5 \rangle \wedge \langle 5I, -5I \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_5$. Also,
 $\because 5 = (-1)(-5) \Rightarrow (-5|5) \wedge (-5|5) \Rightarrow (-5|5) \wedge (-5I|5I) \Rightarrow \langle -5, 5 \rangle \wedge \langle -5I, 5I \rangle \in \mathfrak{R}_5$. It is clear that $\langle 5, -5 \rangle \neq \langle -5, 5 \rangle \wedge \langle 5I, -5I \rangle \neq \langle -5I, 5I \rangle$. So, $\mathfrak{R}_5$ is non neutrosophic antisymmetric relation.

Definition 2.11 [2] Let $H_i^t[I]$, $i = 1, 2, 3$, be three neutrosophic-sets of type-1, type-2, and type-3, respectively. The neutrosophic power-sets of type-1, type-2, and type-3, then:
 $\mathfrak{S}(H_i^t[I]) = \{N_i^t[I] : N_i^t[I] \subseteq H_i^t[I], i = 1, 2, 3\}$ is a neutrosophic power-sets of type-1, type-2, and type-3 respectively.

Theorem 2.7 Let $\mathfrak{U}$ be a neutrosophic relation on neutrosophic power-sets $\mathfrak{S}(H_i^t[I])$ of type-1, type-2, and type-3 respectively, where $i = 1, 2, 3$ and $\mathfrak{U}$ is given by:

$$\mathfrak{U} = \{ \langle H_i^t[I], N_i^t[I] \rangle \in \mathfrak{S}(H_i^t[I]) \times \mathfrak{S}(H_i^t[I]) : H_i^t[I] \subseteq N_i^t[I] \}, \text{ for any } i = 1, 2, 3. \text{ Then neutrosophic relation } \mathfrak{U} \text{ is a neutrosophic partial order relation on } \mathfrak{S}(H_i^t[I]).$$

Proof.

PN₁. Since $N_i^t[I] \subseteq H_i^t[I]$, $\forall N_i^t[I] \in \mathfrak{S}(H_i^t[I])$, and $\forall i = 1, 2, 3$, where H is any arbitrary classical set, then $\langle N_i^t[I], N_i^t[I] \rangle \in \mathfrak{U}$ and $\mathfrak{U}$ is a neutrosophic reflexive relation on $\mathfrak{S}(H_i^t[I])$.

PN₂. Suppose that $\langle H_i^t[I], N_i^t[I] \rangle \wedge \langle N_i^t[I], H_i^t[I] \rangle \in \mathfrak{U}$. From this "neu-hypo" we have $\langle H_i^t[I], N_i^t[I] \rangle \in \mathfrak{U} \Rightarrow H_i^t[I] \subseteq N_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$. Also, $\langle N_i^t[I], H_i^t[I] \rangle \in \mathfrak{U} \Rightarrow N_i^t[I] \subseteq H_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$. By theorem 3.4 in [1], we deduce that $H_i^t[I] = N_i^t[I]$, and consequently, $\mathfrak{U}$ is a neutrosophic antisymmetric relation on $\mathfrak{S}(H_i^t[I])$.

PN₃. Suppose that $\langle H_i^t[I], N_i^t[I] \rangle \wedge \langle N_i^t[I], M_i^t[I] \rangle \in \mathfrak{U}$, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$. So, we get the following Neutrosophic propositions $\langle H_i^t[I], N_i^t[I] \rangle \in \mathfrak{U} \Rightarrow H_i^t[I] \subseteq N_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$ and $\langle N_i^t[I], M_i^t[I] \rangle \in \mathfrak{U} \Rightarrow N_i^t[I] \subseteq M_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$, hence $H_i^t[I] \subseteq M_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1, 2, 3$. So, $\mathfrak{U}$ is a neutrosophic transitive relation on $\mathfrak{S}(H_i^t[I])$. Therefore $\mathfrak{U}$ is a neutrosophic partial order relation on $\mathfrak{S}(H_i^t[I])$. ■

There are some relations defined on neutrosophic sets $\mathbb{Z}[I] = \{a + bI : a, b \in \mathbb{Z}\}$, and $\mathbb{R}[I] = \{a + bI : a, b \in \mathbb{R}\}$ in [11] and [12] which are equivalents to our works.

4. Conclusions

This article presented a new fact related to partial order relation on $H_i^t[I]$, for any $i = 1,2,3$ with theorem and examples as extended for our previous work.

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